

Thermoanalytical investigations of non-oxovanadium(IV) complexes of biphenylphenols

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Abstract : Thermal behaviour of non-oxovanadium(IV) complexes of composition $[VCl_{2-n}(acac)_2(OAr^{1,2})_n]$ (where $OAr^1 = OC_6H_4C_6H_5-2$; $OAr^2 = OC_6H_4C_6H_5-4$; $acac =$ acetylacetonate ion $(CH_3COCHCOCH_3)^-$; $n = 1$ and 2) synthesized by the reaction of $VCl_2(acac)_2$ with the sodium salt of the respective phenols has been studied using thermogravimetric (TG) and differential thermal analysis (DTA) techniques. Thermograms indicate that the complexes undergo decomposition mainly in two steps to yield VO_2 as the final product of decomposition. From initial decomposition temperatures (IDT), the order of thermal stability for complexes has been inferred as $VCl(acac)_2(OAr^1) > V(acac)_2(OAr^1)_2 > VCl(acac)_2(OAr^2) > V(acac)_2(OAr^2)_2$. From the mathematical analysis of TG data, kinetic and thermodynamic parameters viz. energy of activation, frequency factor, order of reaction, entropy of activation etc. at the first and second decomposition stages employing Coats-Redfern, Freeman-Carroll and Horowitz-Metzger equations have been evaluated.

Keywords : Biphenylphenols, Coats-Redfern equation, Freeman-Carroll equation, Horowitz-Metzger equation, kinetic parameters, non-oxovanadium(IV) complexes, TG and DTA.

Introduction

Continuing research interest towards the synthesis of non-oxovanadium(IV) complexes from simple and complex oxovanadium(IV) species is prompted not only by their relevance to biological modeling, catalysis and material sciences but also from the fact that these complexes may display interesting electrochemistry and redox chemistry¹⁻⁸. Although, many non-oxovanadium(IV) complexes have now been structurally and spectroscopically characterized⁹⁻¹², yet reports on their thermal behaviour are lacking. Nevertheless, thermoanalytical investigations of vanadium complexes are of considerable interest both from fundamental and technical point of view like other metal complexes, the final thermolysis product of which as metal oxides are extensively used as catalysts, ceramic colorants, photoconductors and gas sensors. In continuation of our earlier work on thermal decomposition and kinetic studies of non-oxovanadium(IV) complexes^{13,14}, the present investigation describes the thermal behaviour of newly synthesized complexes of composition $[VCl_{2-n}(acac)_2(OAr^{1,2})_n]$ ¹⁵. The kinetic and thermodynamic pa-

rameters from TG data have been computed employing the differential Freeman-Carroll equation, the integral method using Coats-Redfern equation and the approximation method using Horowitz-Metzger equation.

Experimental

The $[VCl_2(acac)_2]$ was prepared from $[VO(acac)_2]$ by the literature method¹⁶. The 2- and 4-phenylphenols with sharp melting points, 57 °C and 168 °C respectively were used.

For the preparation of sodium salts of 2- and 4-phenylphenols, to the solution of 2-phenylphenol/4-phenylphenol (4.0 g, 23 mmol) in tetrahydrofuran (40 ml), was added NaH (0.56 g, 23 mmol) slowly. The reactants were stirred on a magnetic stirrer for 6-8 h during which, the solution turned light brown in color. The solution containing sodium salt of the respective phenols, without isolating the sodium 2-phenyl and 4-phenylphenoxides in solid form, was used for carrying out different reactions for the preparation of vanadium(IV) complexes.

For the preparation of complexes of composition $[VCl_{2-n}(OAr^{1,2})_n]$, to the tetrahydrofuran solution containing sodium 2-phenyl/4-phenylphenoxide (4.48 g, 23 mmol), a suspension of $VCl_2(acac)_2$ (3.75 g, 11.5 mmol/7.5 g, 23 mmol) in THF (50 ml) was added in separate experiments. The reaction mixture was initially stirred for 3–4 h and was then refluxed for about 5 h to ensure the completion of reaction. Formation of white solid was observed during the course of the reaction. It was removed by filtration and was identified as sodium chloride. The excess solvent was then distilled off and the concentrate was treated repeatedly with diethyl ether and petroleum ether and dried under vacuo, whereupon light to dark green colored solids were obtained. These were recrystallized from tetrahydrofuran.

Thermograms of powdered samples were recorded on simultaneous TG-DTA Shimadzu DT-40 thermal analyzer in air at a heating rate of $20\text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ using platinum crucible. The TG graph obtained were used for mathematical analysis of decomposition steps. The values of kinetic parameters viz. energy of activation (E^*), frequency factor (Z) and activation entropy (ΔS^*) were approximated using Freeman-Carroll, Coats-Redfern and Horowitz-Metzger equations.

Results and discussion

All the complexes are green to dark green solids and are quite stable in dry air. Thermal decomposition data of bare vanadium(IV) complexes are summarized in Table 1. A perusal of TG/DTA curves for I-IV complexes recorded in air (Figs. 1–4) have shown these to be stable upto 135.2, 93.0, 87.8 and 78.20 $^\circ\text{C}$ respectively.

After this temperature the complexes undergo decomposition into two distinct steps. It is quite noteworthy that the complexes derived from 2-phenylphenol have displayed higher initial temperature of decomposition indicative of their high thermal stability relative to complexes synthesized from 4-phenylphenol presumably indicating that the former phenolic ligand is held more tightly around metal than the latter. Of two series of complexes, chloro complexes have been observed to depict higher thermal stability than non-chloro complexes suggesting thereby that the replacement of both the chloride ions in precursor $[VCl_2(acac)_2]$ with phenoxide ion results in decreasing stability. For $[VCl(acac)_2(OAr^{1,2})]$ complexes the weight loss amounting to 42.87% and 40.96% respectively in the first decompositional stage has been found to correspond to the formation of $VOCl(OAr^{1,2})$ as the probable intermediate as a result of the removal of both the acetylacetonate groups. This is in contrast to the proposi-

Table 1. Thermal data of non-oxovanadium(IV) complexes

Complex	Initial decomp. temp. ($^\circ\text{C}$)	Stages of decomp.	Decomp. range ($^\circ\text{C}$)	TGA data		DTA data	
				% wt. loss Obsd. (Calcd.)	Decomp. products	Peak temp. (%)	Peak nature
$VCl(acac)_2(OAr^1)$ (I)	135.2	Two	135.2–251.6	42.87 (41.62)	$VOCl(OAr^1)$	251.6	Exo
			251.6–468.3	38.53 (40.08)	VO_2	442.9	Exo
$V(acac)_2(OAr^1)_2$ (II)	93.0	Two	93.0–255.0	52.78 (54.85)	$VO(acac)(OAr^1)$	255.0	Exo
			255.0–520.0	32.87 (31.0)	VO_2	392.6	Exo
$VCl(acac)_2(OAr^2)$ (III)	87.8	Two	87.8–251.4	40.96 (41.62)	$VOCl(OAr^2)$	233.1	Exo
			251.4–488.5	39.84 (40.08)	VO_2	454.8	Exo
$V(acac)_2(OAr^2)_2$ (IV)	78.2	Two	78.2–256.7	41.62 (42.93)	$VO(acac)(OAr^2)$	238.4	Exo
			256.7–522.4	42.07 (42.93)	VO_2	462.1	Exo

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

OC₆H₄OMe-4; OC₆H₄Bu¹-4, OC₆H₂Bu₂^{1,2,6}-Me-4 and OC₆H₄NO₂-4)¹⁷. On the other hand, for [V(acac)₂(OAr^{1,2})₂] the weight loss of 40.18% and 41.62% in the respective complexes in first stage of decomposition accounted for the proposition of [VO(acac)(OAr^{1,2})] as the likely intermediate. Strikingly, this is also contrary to the proposition of VO(acac)₂ as intermediate from the thermal decomposition of [V(acac)₂(OC₆H₄OMe-4)₂] and [V(acac)₂OC₆H₄Bu¹-4]₂] complexes and of proposed intermediate as [VO(acac)₂(OC₆H₄NO₂-4)] from [V(acac)₂(OC₆H₄NO₂-4)₂]. However, the formation of [VO(acac)(OAr^{1,2})] as intermediate in the present case is in consonance with that formed from the thermal decomposition of [V(acac)₂(OC₆H₂Bu₂^{1,2,6}-Me-4)₂].

For all the complexes the weight loss in second decomposition stage corresponded to the formation of VO₂ as the final product rather than V₂O₅ which is a striking feature of complexes studied herein. It is pertinent to mention here that thermal decomposition of vanadium(IV) oxalate¹⁸ and vanadium(IV) formate¹⁹ is known to yield V₂O₃ and VO₂ respectively as the ultimate residue. The two step decomposition for the complexes may be represented as :

The DTA curves of the complexes have shown exothermic peaks suggesting thereby that the entire thermal decomposition of complexes is an exothermic process.

Kinetic parameters : One of the widespread quantitative applications of thermogravimetry has been the evaluation of kinetic parameters such as rate constants, apparent activation energies, reaction order and pre-exponential factors. Hence, the kinetics associated with the thermal decomposition of complexes have been evaluated from the mathematical analysis of the TGA curves. Multiple analysis methods have been described in literature for computing kinetic parameters by simplifying the general kinetic equation. These methods are based on two as-

tion of VOCl(acac) as the probable intermediate from complexes of composition [VCl(acac)₂(OAr)] (OAr =

assumptions (i) thermal and diffusion barriers are negligible and (ii) Arrhenius equation is valid. The kinetics of solid state reactions is studied generally by isothermal and non-isothermal methods. The isothermal method was mostly employed for the study of the kinetics of solid state reactions in earlier literature. But over the three decades, non-isothermal methods have drawn much attention as different steps of reaction can be distinguished by non-isothermal methods especially by DTA and simultaneous TG-DTA or DTG-DTA.

In the present work, the mathematical analysis of TG curves, has been carried out using Freeman-Carroll, Coats-Redfern and Horowitz-Metzger equations.

Freeman-Carroll equation : Of various methods, Freeman-Carroll method²⁰ is the oldest and most criticized but still generally used. The advantage of Freeman-Carroll method is that the parameters of temperature and time can be varied. At the same time the order of reaction and energy of activation can be obtained in a single experiment. The following Freeman-Carroll expression was used to evaluate various kinetic parameters,

$$\frac{\Delta \log (dW/dt)}{\Delta \log W_r} = \frac{-(E^*/2.303R)\Delta(1/T)}{\Delta \log W_r} + n \quad (3)$$

where $W_r = W_\alpha - W$, W_r i.e. the difference between the loss in weight after completion of the reaction (W_α) and the loss in weight upto time t (W), W_α is the mass loss at the completion of the reaction, W is the mass loss upto time t , T is the temperature on absolute scale, n is the order of reaction. R is gas constant in Joules and E^* is the energy of activation in kJ mol^{-1} . W_r and T can be directly obtained from the TG traces. dW/dt is the rate of weight loss with time t which is calculated by converting temperature slopes, dW/dT into time slopes dW/dt using the relation :

$$dW/dt = dW/dT \times dT/dt \quad (3a)$$

The plots of $\Delta \log (dW/dt)/\Delta \log W_r$ vs $\Delta(1/T)/\Delta \log W_r$ were drawn to obtain the order of reaction from intercept. The decomposition of complexes from intercept was found to be of first order.

Since the order of reaction is unity, Freeman-Carroll equation can be written as :

$$\log \left[\frac{dW/dt}{W_r} \right] = \frac{-E^*}{2.303RT} + \log Z \quad (3b)$$

where Z is frequency factor. Plot of $\log [dW/dt/W_r]$ against T^{-1} (Fig. 5) were drawn. They gave straight lines in all cases with slopes $-E^*/2.303R$ from which E^* values were obtained. Z was calculated from the intercept.

Fig. 5

Coats-Redfern equation : Compared to many developed methods for the evaluation of kinetic parameters from TG data, Coats-Redfern equation has been described to be less tedious, giving satisfactory kinetic analysis of thermogravimetric data. Hence, the mathematical analysis of TG data was carried out using Coats-Redfern equation^{21,22} in the following form assuming the decomposition of complexes to follow first order kinetics inferred from Freeman-Carroll method as :

$$\begin{aligned} & \log \left[\ln \frac{W_\alpha}{W_\alpha - W} \right] \\ &= \log \left[\frac{ZR}{\Phi E^*} \left(1 - \frac{2RT}{E^*} \right) \right] - \frac{E^*}{2.303RT} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where, W_α = mass loss at the completion of the reaction, W = mass loss at time t , Φ = linear rate of heating.

The plots of $\log \left\{ \ln [W_\alpha/(W_\alpha - W)T^2] \right\}$ vs $1/T$ were drawn (Fig. 6) which gave straight lines in all cases with a slope of $-E^*/2.303R$ from which the activation energy was calculated.

Horowitz-Metzger equation : This is an approximate integral method²³ similar to but even simpler than earlier

Fig. 6

described approximate methods²⁴ and is considered as complement to the more detailed slope plotting methods for quick analysers.

The following Horowitz-Metzger equation was used for the computation of kinetic parameters,

$$\log \left[\log \frac{W_\alpha}{W_r} \right] = \frac{E^* \theta}{2.303 RT_s^2} - \log 2.303 \quad (5)$$

where W_α , W_r and W are the same as mentioned above.

$$\theta = T - T_s \quad (5b)$$

T_s is the temperature at which decomposition is maximum.

The plots of $\log [\log W_\alpha / W_r]$ vs θ were drawn (Fig. 7) which gave straight lines in all the cases with the slope $E^*/2.303RT_s^2$ from which E^* values were obtained.

Fig. 7

Z was calculated using the following equation :

$$\frac{E^*}{RT_s^2} = \frac{Z}{e^{-E^*/RT_s}} \quad (6)$$

The other parameters viz. entropy of activation ΔS^* ²⁵ and free energy G^* ²⁶ were computed from the standard relations.

A perusal of data (Table 2) has revealed some differences in the kinetic parameters computed by different methods. In the present work the difference in the values of activation energy obtained from three equations may be attributed to the fact that different equations involve different limitations. Of the three methods, Horowitz-Metzger equation gave the lowest E^* and more negative ΔS^* values. It is quite noteworthy that complex of composition $[V(acac)_2(OAr^1)_2]$ gave consistent values of E^* at both first and second stage of decomposition by all the three employed methods. It is important to note that the magnitudes of various kinetic parameters by the same equation are quite comparable. The negative values of ΔS^* indicate that the activation complex has a more ordered structure than the reactants²⁷. The low value of Z suggest that the reactions are slower than normal^{28,29}.

No correlation however observed between the kinetic parameters and order of thermal stability may be ascribed to the fact that decisive criteria in kinetics are different from those describing thermal stability.

Conclusion :

The newly synthesized non-oxovanadium(IV) complexes have two stage decomposition pattern yielding VO_2 as the final product of decomposition which is quite striking as most of the vanadium complexes decompose to give V_2O_5 as final residue. The low-valent vanadium oxides are unique as these exhibit excellent optical, electrical and electrochemical properties, thus non-oxovanadium(IV) complexes synthesized seem to be promising precursors to afford low-valent VO_2 . Of three methods, employed in the present work, Horowitz-Metzger method though assumed mathematically less accurate than integral methods yet is quite simple and easy for evaluation of kinetic parameters.

Coats-Redfern method described to be more accurate in literature is considerable time consuming method. Freeman-Carroll method seemed to be complementary to Coats-

Table 2. Kinetic data of non-oxovanadium(IV) complexes

Complex	Method	Stage of decomposition	E* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Z (s ⁻¹)	ΔS* (kJ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	G* (kJ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)
VCl(acac) ₂ (OAr ¹) ₂ (I)	F-C	1st	56.17	2.98 × 10 ³	-182.72	91.06 × 10 ³
	C-R		52.15	3.6	-181.16	90.27 × 10 ³
	H-M		37.98	1.32	-227.92	113.4 × 10 ³
	F-C	2nd	30.62	1.45 × 10 ³	-188.10	117.22 × 10 ³
	C-R		37.58	8.9	-175.49	109.36 × 10 ³
	H-M		67.60	1.68	-228.06	142.10 × 10 ³
V(acac) ₂ (OAr ¹) ₂ (II)	F-C	1st	39.14	4.6 × 10 ³	-179.2	90.14 × 10 ³
	C-R		38.42	6.9	-175.92	88.53 × 10 ³
	H-M		33.91	1.06	-229.70	115.50 × 10 ³
	F-C	2nd	31.64	2.6 × 10 ²	-184.30	96.4 × 10 ³
	C-R		36.66	7.2	-175.79	91.97 × 10 ³
	H-M		36.66	1.09	-210.68	127.5 × 10 ³
VCl(acac) ₂ (OAr ²) (III)	F-C	1st	43.09	1.74 × 10 ²	-187.60	98.16 × 10 ³
	C-R		37.07	1.14	-191.13	99.99 × 10 ³
	H-M		21.26	2.75	-222.09	127.36 × 10 ³
	F-C	2nd	38.57	2.25 × 10 ²	-168.30	112.6 × 10 ³
	C-R		35.13	9.2	-175.73	116.54 × 10 ³
	H-M		31.63	2.51	-224.82	165.4 × 10 ³
V(acac) ₂ (OAr ²) ₂ (IV)	F-C	1st	36.25	1.51 × 10 ²	-207.61	104.64 × 10 ³
	C-R		32.92	2.0	-186.12	93.65 × 10 ³
	H-M		14.68	2.05	-229.21	120.07 × 10 ³
	F-C	2nd	34.05	0.99 × 10 ²	-212.9	132.67 × 10 ³
	C-R		28.07	4.0	-182.14	113.5 × 10 ³
	H-M		20.88	1.90	-226.62	147.7 × 10 ³

Redfern method. The negative values for entropy (ΔS*) indicate that the activated complex has more ordered structure than the reactants and the reactions are slower than normal.

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Sharma *et al.* : Thermoanalytical investigations of non-oxovanadium(IV) complexes *etc.*

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